

MONIMED - Monitoring Mediterranean climate-smart forestry practices for climate resilience and ecosystem service provision

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Deliverable 3.2. Evaluation of the performance of the practices

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Abstract

This deliverable describes the performance of the practices implemented in the project, as well as the previous conventional practices applied in the same areas. The two objectives are, firstly, to quantify the new Climate-Smart Forestry practices implemented in February 2025, and, secondly, to compare these practices using new monitoring parameters linked to multifunctional management, biodiversity conservation, mitigation capacity and climate resilience.

The first section provides a brief introduction to the deliverable. The second section summarises the actions implemented in the three sites. The third section quantifies the effects of the practices in Requesens. Sections four and five reproduce the same information for the Montesquiú and Montnegre-Corredor field trials, respectively.

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1. Introduction

Mediterranean forests, shaped by past intensive and simplified management, now face heightened vulnerability due to rural abandonment and climate change. These legacy of forest structures increase exposure to drought, pests, and wildfire, while ecosystem service provision is at risk. Demonstration projects over recent decades have evaluated how silvicultural interventions influence forest growth, vitality, and fire risk mitigation. The MONIMED project advances **adaptive management through climate-smart forestry**, combining multifunctional objectives with closer-to-nature approaches. Pilot sites under conventional regimes (5–10 years of monitoring) are compared with new trials applying integrative multifunctional management and process-oriented strategies. Long-term assessment incorporates novel indicators addressing biodiversity support, carbon sequestration, and resilience to climatic pressures.

This report describes the **performance of the practices implemented** within the MONIMED project. In first, the document summaries the **effects of the two new Climate-Smart Forestry practices implemented in February 2025 in forest structure and characteristics**: the close-to-Nature and the preparation to natural dynamics field trials. This evaluation is based on the comparison between the initial inventories developed on Autumn 2024, and the final inventories, developed on Autumn 2025. In second place, the document compares the implemented practices using **new monitoring parameters** linked to multifunctional management, biodiversity conservation, mitigation capacity and climate resilience of the system.

2. The implemented practices

This chapter briefly summarises the practices evaluated in this deliverable, to easily follow up the results. A more detailed description of the practices can be consulted at (Pascual, et al., 2025) and (Pascual, et al., 2025b). The project is developed in the Mediterranean area of Catalonia (NE Spain), in forests dominated by *Quercus ilex*, *Quercus humilis* and *Pinus sylvestris*. The field trials are established in three sites:

- A Holm oak forest in La Albera protected area (Girona).
- A mixed forest of *Pinus sylvestris* and oaks in the Montesquiú natural park (Barcelona).
- A Holm oak forest in the Montnegre-Corredor natural park (Barcelona).

2.1. Holm oak forest in La Albera protected area (Girona)

This site is in La Albera protected area, in Requesens estate, an area highly vulnerable to climate change impacts. Holm oak is the dominant species in a highly dense forest with an irregular structure, unmanaged for approximately 80 years.

The silvicultural practices were applied in 2015 and 2025. A detailed description of the practices can be found at (Pascual, et al., 2025). Table 1 summarizes the four practices, implemented in a surface of about 1 ha, and complemented with a control plot with no intervention.

Table 1. Practices implemented at Requesens site.

Practices	Treatment	Description	Evaluation	Year
Conventional silvicultural practices	Low intensity treatment	Low thinning clearing with the objective to adapt the forest to a regular structure	10%-reduction in basal area 18%-reduction in density No changes in canopy cover	2015
	High intensity treatment	Selection treatment and intense understory clearing to adapt forest to an irregular structure	33%-reduction in basal area 43%-reduction in density 29%-reduction of canopy cover	2015
New Climate-Smart Forestry practices	Close-to-Nature Silviculture	Individual-tree silvicultural method, prioritizing the selection of high-quality trees for multiple objectives	8%-reduction in basal area 14%-reduction in density 2%-reduction in canopy cover	2025
	Preparation to natural dynamics	Promotion of forest maturity and restore complex ecological processes	3%-reduction in basal area 1%-reduction in density No changes in canopy cover	2025
Control	No intervention			2015

2.2. Mixed forest of *Pinus sylvestris* and oaks in the Montesquiú natural park (Barcelona)

This site is in Montesquiú natural park, in mixed forest of *Pinus sylvestris* and *Quercus humilis*, unmanaged for approximately 40 years. The forest had suffered last decade tree decline episodes and plagues, which park managers attribute to episodes of drought as the main cause.

The silvicultural practices were applied in 2015 and 2024-2025. A detailed description of the practices can be found at (Pascual, et al., 2025). Table 2 summarizes the five practices, implemented in a surface of about 1 ha, and complemented with two control plots with no intervention.

Table 2. Practices implemented at Montesquiú site.

Practices	Treatment	Description	Evaluation	Year
Conventional silvicultural practices	Low intensity treatment	Understory clearing with the objective to reduce resources competition. No effects on Scots pine	4%-reduction in basal area 17%-reduction in density	2015
	High intensity treatment	Low thinning and intense understory clearing with the objective to reduce tree competition	17%-reduction in basal area 24%-reduction in density	2015
	Pine logging	Elimination of Scots pines to accelerate the replacement of pines by oaks and evaluate the oaks' future development	75%-reduction in basal area 64%-reduction in density	2015
New Climate-Smart Forestry practices	Close-to-Nature Silviculture	Individual-tree silvicultural method, prioritizing the selection of high-quality trees for multiple objectives	28%-reduction in basal area 26%-reduction in density	2025
	Preparation to natural dynamics	Promotion of forest maturity and restore complex ecological processes	8%-reduction in basal area 4%-reduction in density	2025
Control	No intervention			2015
Control2	No intervention			2025

2.3. Holm oak forest in the Montnegre-Corredor natural park (Barcelona)

This site is in Montnegre-Corredor natural park, a Holm oak forest with a high vulnerability to pests, forest fires and droughts.

The silvicultural practices were applied in 2020 and 2025. A detailed description of the practices can be found at (Pascual, et al., 2025). Table 3 summarizes the four practices, complemented with a control plot with no intervention. As the affected area is different in each practice, the surface occupied is indicated in the Treatment's column.

Table 3. Practices implemented at Montnegre site.

Practices	Treatment	Description	Evaluation	Year
Conventional silvicultural practices	Irregular forest management model (5.4 ha)	Thinning (gentle felling in patches of holm oak and the densest patches of stone pine), coppice management and selective clearing	8%-reduction in basal area 19%-reduction in density 14%-reduction in canopy cover	2020
New Climate-Smart Forestry practices	Close-to-Nature Silviculture (1ha)	Individual-tree silvicultural method, prioritizing the selection of high-quality trees for multiple objectives	16%-reduction in basal area 36%-reduction in density 22%-reduction in canopy cover	2025
	Preparation to natural dynamics (1 ha)	Promotion of forest maturity and restore complex ecological processes	6%-reduction in basal area 2%-reduction in density No changes in canopy cover	2025
Control	No intervention (1.9 ha)			2020

3. Holm oak forest in La Albera protected area (Girona)

This chapter evaluates the performance of the practices implemented in the Holm oak forest in La Albera protected area. This evaluation uses **three different datasets**:

- The forests inventories developed in LIFE MIDMACC project (LIFE12 ENV/ES/000536, <http://medacc-life.eu/>), between 2014 and 2018. The inventory followed the criteria established in the monitoring protocol contained in (Savé, et al., 2015)
- The initial inventory of MONIMED project, performed in Autumn 2024 to capture the initial condition of the site. The inventory followed the indications and criteria set in the Monitoring protocol (Pascual, et al., 2025b).
- The final inventory of MONIMED project, performed in Autumn 2025 to evaluate the implemented practices. The inventory followed the indications and criteria set in the Monitoring protocol (Pascual, et al., 2025b).

Based on the three datasets, **two different analyses have been performed**:

- The evaluation of the new Climate-Smart Forestry practices: The intensity of the interventions has been defined using the initial and final inventory of MONIMED project.
- The comparison of the practices using new monitoring parameters: One of the novelties of MONIMED project was to include new monitoring parameters linked to multifunctional management, biodiversity conservation, mitigation capacity and climate resilience of the system. This analysis shows the results of these parameters for all the practices using the common inventory performed on Autumn 2024.

All the results in this deliverable are shown per treatment, that's mean, that the values presented are the mean value of the three permanent circular subplots per treatment.

3.1. Evaluation of the new Climate-Smart Forestry practices

Two new Climate-Smart Forestry practices were implemented in February 2025 with the MONIMED project. Before and after the implementation, forest inventories were developed on Autumn 2024 and Autumn 2025. The comparison between both inventories allow to evaluate the intensity of the interventions.

- **Close-to-Nature Silviculture Plot:** Application of the individual-tree silvicultural method, where high-quality trees for multiple objectives (biodiversity conservation, timber production, and natural regeneration) were selected. Specific silvicultural interventions were applied to optimize their development, including reducing direct competition. The objective is to make a light intervention with an important impact on future trees, but without compromising the budget. The practice's intensity was:
 - An 8%-reduction in basal area and a 14%-reduction in density.
 - A 2%-reduction in canopy cover.

- **Plot of preparation to natural dynamics** in non-productive stands: Application of concrete interventions to promote forest maturity and restore complex ecological processes by minimizing human influence. The interventions included the increase of coarse woody debris stocks both on the forest floor (through tree felling) and standing (via tree girdling), the alleviation of direct competition to larger-diameter trees and the promotion of vertical heterogeneity. The practice's intensity was:
 - A 3%-reduction in basal area and a 1%-reduction in density.
 - No changes in the canopy cover.

Table 4 summarizes the initial density and basal area of each treatment area initially, the same numbers after the implementation of the forest management, and the percentage of change. The intensity of the new CSF practices is smaller than the conventional practices, as consequence of the objective to focus more on concrete interventions with low intensity and budget, but that allow to maximize the ecological benefits. The numbers show a decreasing trend in the intensity of treatments, covering a wide range of possibilities that will allow evaluating the effect of the intensity in the several ecological variables.

Table 4. Summary of the density and basal area per treatment, before the forest management (Pre), after the management (Post) and percentage of change (Change).

Practices	Treatment	Density			Basal area			Canopy cover		
		Pre (ft/ha)	Post (ft/ha)	Change (%)	Pre (m ² /ha)	Post (m ² /ha)	Change (%)	Pre (%)	Post (%)	Change (%)
Conventional practices (2014-15)	Low intensity	2,812	2,292	-18%	28.1	25.4	-10%	72	72	0%
	High intensity	2,599	1,485	-43%	33.5	22.5	-33%	85	60	-29%
New CSF practices (2024-25)	Close-to-nature	3,310	2,833	-14%	37.0	34.0	-8%	85	83	-2%
	Natural dynamics	2,759	2,727	-1%	41.7	40.3	-3%	82	82	0%
Control		2,164	2,164	-	32.8	32.8	-	77	77	0%

3.2. Evaluation of the practices using new monitoring parameters

All the practices are evaluated using the monitoring parameters established in the monitoring protocol (Pascual, et al., 2025b). For this evaluation, the dataset of the initial inventory of MONIMED project (Autumn 2024) is used for all the practices. Moreover, the results of the final inventory of the MONIMED project (Autumn 2025) are shown in the two new practices, to capture the final situation of the forest after the new treatments. Table 5 summaries the monitored variables and is followed by a detailed description of each variable, the means to measure, frequency and specifications, as is included in (Pascual, et al., 2025b).

Table 5. Summary of the monitoring variables, specifying the methodology and periodicity of the monitoring.

	Variable	Measured variables	Methodology	Periodicity
Measuring the mitigation capacity	Carbon storage in soil	Soil organic carbon (Mg/ha) Litter (Mg/ha)	Soil sampling and analysis	Initial (After 3 years)
	Carbon storage in forest	Carbon stocks above and below ground (Mg/ha) Diameter at breast height (cm)	Forest inventory Allometry	Initial (After 3 years)
Measuring the resistance to droughts	Forest health status	Forest decline (%) Tree mortality (number) Defoliation (%) Decolouration (%)	Forest health sampling	Initial Final (After 3 years)
	Soil moisture	Soil water content (SWC)	Humidity sensors	Continuous
Measuring the restauration of other ecosystem services	Biodiversity	Potential Biodiversity Index (IBP) (index value) Tree richness (number) Vertical structure (number) Standing deadwood (number) Lying deadwood (number) Large trees (number) Habitat-trees (number) Openness (%) Temporal continuity of the woody state (presence) Wet macrohabitats (number) Rocky macrohabitats (number)	Vegetation surveys	Initial Final ^{1,2} (After 3 years)
	Wood provision	Wood biomass (Mg/ha) Diameter at breast height (cm)	Forest inventory	Initial Final ¹ (After 3 years)
Measuring the reduction of fire risk	Forest structure	Tree density (trees/ha) Resprouting (number) Canopy cover (%)	Forest inventory	Initial Final ¹ (After 3 years)
	Forest fuel continuity	Crown fire hazard (index value) Fuel type cover (%) Fuel height (m) Distance between fuel types (m) Understorey biovolume (m ³ /ha)	Fuel identification and classification	Initial Final ³ (After 3 years)

¹ In subplots of closer-to-nature silviculture

² In subplots of preparation to natural dynamics

³ Only the Crown fire hazard

3.2.1. Measuring the mitigation capacity

Mitigation capacity is quantified using two variables: carbon storage in soil and in forests.

Carbon storage in soils. The carbon content of the topsoil and litter is estimated (MgC/ha). A minor amendment to the methodology has been introduced, as detailed in

(Pascual, et al., 2025b). The monitoring protocol establishes the following procedure for preparing litter samples:

Litter samples are oven-dried at 40°C for five days, then weighed, mixed to create a composite sample and pulverised using a coffee grinder prior to carbon analysis. The organic carbon content of the litter samples is analysed by elemental analysis of the pulverised sample. Litter carbon quantification (MgC/ha) is calculated based on the total weight of the collected litter, the sampled area, and the litter carbon content. See pages 13 and 14 of (Pascual, et al., 2025b).

However, this process was deemed unacceptable due to the large number of samples (48) required, so the following protocol was applied instead:

Litter samples are oven-dried at 70 °C for five days and then weighed to obtain dry mass. The litter carbon content is estimated by assuming that 47.2% of the dry biomass corresponds to carbon, following (Ispikoudis, et al., 2024), and the results are expressed in tonnes of carbon per hectare (MgC/ha).

Table 6 shows the carbon content of the soil and litter, after the sampling in 2024. Total carbon stocks are very similar in all treatments at around 47 tonnes of carbon per hectare, except for the natural dynamic treatment, where the total value is lower at 39.7 MgC/ha. The organic content of the soil and litter will be measured again in three years' time, by which point some initial changes and trends among the practices may have become apparent.

Table 6. Soil, litter and total carbon content in each treatment in 2024.

Practice	Treatment	Soil organic content (SOC, MgC/ha)	Litter organic content (MgC/ha)	Total carbon stocks (MgC/ha)
Conventional practices	Low intensity	42.6	5.2	47.8
	High intensity	43.5	4.2	47.7
New CSF practices	Close-to-nature	41.1	4.9	46.0
	Natural dynamics	35.4	4.3	39.7
Control		43.6	3.6	47.2

Carbon storage in forests. This is assessed through the quantification of aboveground carbon stock, using tree diameter at breast height (DBH), and understorey carbon stock as key indicators. Aboveground carbon stock is estimated using species-specific allometric models, which allow the calculation of carbon allocation (MgC/ha) in trunks, bark, branches, and roots. These models are obtained from the *Allometr App del Laboratori Forestal Català* (<https://laboratoriforestal.creaf.cat/allometrapp/>), and are presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Allometric equations for the tree species inventoried in MONIMED project, extracted from the Laboratori Forestal Català.

Species	Dependent variable	Independent variable	Equation	Parameter a	Parameter b	Parameter c
<i>Arbutus unedo</i>	BAT	DBH	$BAT = a \cdot DBH^b$	0.1501	2.2602	
<i>Erica arborea</i>	BAT	DBH	$BAT = a \cdot DBH^b$	0.4067	2.0064	
<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	BAT	DBH	$BAT = a \cdot DBH^b$	0.2071	2.1943	
<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>	BAT	DBH	$BAT = a \cdot DBH^b$	0.0985	2.4792	
<i>Ilex aquifolium</i>	BAT	DBH	$BAT = a \cdot DBH^b$	0.1851	2.1592	
<i>Pinus halepensis</i>	BAT	DBH	$BAT = a \cdot DBH^b$	0.1229	2.2220	
<i>Pinus nigra</i>	BAT	DBH	$BAT = a \cdot DBH^b$	0.0532	2.4994	
<i>Pinus pinea</i>	BAT	DBH	$BAT = a \cdot DBH^b$	0.0574	2.4369	
<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	BAT	DBH	$BAT = a \cdot DBH^b$	0.08411	2.3408	
<i>Quercus humilis</i>	BAT	DBH	$BAT = a \cdot DBH^b$	0.1118	2.3538	
<i>Quercus ilex</i>	BAT	DBH	$BAT = a \cdot DBH^b$	0.1647	2.2671	
<i>Quercus suber</i>	BAT	DBH	$BAT = a \cdot DBH^b$	0.0445	2.4230	
<i>Acer campestre</i>	BAT	DBH / Ht ¹	$BAT = a \cdot DBH^b \cdot Ht^c$	0.0779	2.0640	0.5050
<i>Acer monspessulanum</i>	BAT	DBH / Ht ¹	$BAT = a \cdot DBH^b \cdot Ht^c$	0.0780	2.0640	0.5050
<i>Acer opalus</i>	BAT	DBH / Ht ¹	$BAT = a \cdot DBH^b \cdot Ht^c$	0.0780	2.0640	0.5050
<i>Buxus sempervirens</i>	BAT	DBH / Ht ¹	$BAT = a \cdot DBH^b \cdot Ht^c$	0.0830	1.9379	0.7478
<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	BAT	DBH / Ht ¹	$BAT = a \cdot DBH^b \cdot Ht^c$	0.0779	2.0640	0.5050
<i>Juniperus communis</i>	BAT	DBH / Ht ¹	$BAT = a \cdot DBH^b \cdot Ht^c$	0.0596	2.0454	0.5400
<i>Phillyrea latifolia</i>	BAT	DBH / Ht ¹	$BAT = a \cdot DBH^b \cdot Ht^c$	0.0830	1.9379	0.7479
<i>Sorbus aria</i>	BAT	DBH / Ht ¹	$BAT = a \cdot DBH^b \cdot Ht^c$	0.0779	2.0640	0.5050
<i>Sorbus torminalis</i>	BAT	DBH / Ht ¹	$BAT = a \cdot DBH^b \cdot Ht^c$	0.0779	2.0640	0.5050

The ratio of organic matter to carbon stocks is 2.1 g/g (Gracia, et al., 1999). This means that 2.1 g of organic matter is equivalent to 1 g of carbon, which is an estimation of soils with lower carbon fraction (Klingenuß, et al., 2014). The total aerial biomass (MgC/ha) is calculated, and the carbon stocks are estimated by dividing this figure by 2.1 (approximately half). Table 8 shows the aerial carbon stocks in each treatment plot. The values oscillate between 55 and 83 Mg/ha. The effects of low- and high-intensity conventional practices are still evident 10 years after implementation.

¹ Some of the tree species has an allometric equation dependent of height. This value is not available in the dataset. For this reason, we assume an average height of 2.5 metres, as these are shrub species that have a tree-like appearance but rarely exceed that height.

Table 8. Aerial carbon stock in each practice and treatment, in 2024 and 2025.

Practice	Treatment	Aerial carbon stock (MgC/ha)					
		2024			2025		
		Other species	Holm oak	Total	Other species	Holm oak	Total
Conventional practices	Low intensity	6.0	42.3	48.3			
	High intensity	5.1	50.2	55.3			
New CSF practices	Close-to-nature	29.3	38.6	67.9	25.6	37.5	63.1
	Natural dynamics	14.3	68.6	82.9	14.3	65.3	79.6
Control		7.0	68.5	75.5			

Understorey carbon stock is estimated through 10-metre transects, where the vegetation cover and mean height are recorded. Multiplying these values together gives the biovolume of the understorey layer. Biomass is then estimated through biovolume-based allometric models for shrub communities obtained from the *Allometr App* developed by the *Laboratori Forestal Català* (Table 9).

Table 9. Allometric equations for the understorey species inventoried at MONIMED project, extracted from the *Laboratori Forestal Català*.

Species	Dependent variable	Independent variable	Equation	Parameter a	Parameter b
<i>Arbutus unedo</i>	BAT	PHV ²	BAT = a · PHV ^a b	0.397303	1.077385
<i>Arctostaphylos uva-ursi</i>	BAT	PHV	BAT = a · PHV ^a b	0.519963	0.244888
<i>Buxus sempervirens</i>	BAT	PHV	BAT = a · PHV ^a b	1.058090	0.684895
<i>Cistus albidus</i>	BAT	PHV	BAT = a · PHV ^a b	0.484067	0.633012
<i>Cistus salvifolius</i>	BAT	PHV	BAT = a · PHV ^a b	0.403208	0.861827
<i>Erica arborea</i>	BAT	PHV	BAT = a · PHV ^a b	0.882044	0.922365
<i>Ligustrum vulgare</i>	BAT	PHV	BAT = a · PHV ^a b	0.322475	0.810576
<i>Phillyrea latifolia</i>	BAT	PHV	BAT = a · PHV ^a b	0.310581	0.750984
<i>Pistacia lentiscus</i>	BAT	PHV	BAT = a · PHV ^a b	2.172286	0.865432
<i>Quercus ilex</i>	BAT	PHV	BAT = a · PHV ^a b	0.732715	0.737577
<i>Rosa sp.</i>	BAT	PHV	BAT = a · PHV ^a b	0.974249	0.939642
<i>Viburnum lantana</i>	BAT	PHV	BAT = a · PHV ^a b	0.287159	0.704542

The same ratio of organic matter to carbon stocks is applied as for the aerial carbon stocks, first estimating the total aerial biomass and then dividing this figure by 2.1. Table 10 shows the understorey carbon stock in each treatment. These values are very low ranging from 0.5 to 0.6 MgC/ha. Values in conventional practices are higher due to the openness of canopy cover, particularly in high-intensity treatment, which allow more light to reach the ground and facilitate understorey expansion. The new CSF practices result in much lower understorey carbon stocks.

² PHV means biovolume.

Table 10. Understory carbon stock in each practice and treatment.

Practice	Treatment	Understory carbon stock (MgC/ha)
		2024
Conventional practices	Low intensity	2.8
	High intensity	3.2
New CSF practices	Close-to-nature	0.5
	Natural dynamics	0.6
Control		1.7

3.2.2. Measuring the resistance to droughts

Drought resistance is quantified using two variables: forest health status and soil moisture.

Forest health status. This is quantified as the percentage of forest decline, which is calculated by measuring the percentage of defoliation (the number of leaves absent compared to the number of leaves present on a healthy tree) and the percentage of foliage discolouration (the number of non-green leaves compared to the number of green leaves present on a healthy tree) in ten crown of trees per treatment.

Table 11 shows the forest decay in 2024 and 2025. The results show a slow increase in forest decay in 2025, which is more evident in the close-to-nature treatment. However, two years is insufficient time to observe a trend or find significant differences between the practices. This analysis will be performed again in 2028, when more significant effects are expected.

Table 11. Percentage of forest decline in 2024 and 2025.

Practice	Treatment	Forest decline (%)	
		2024	2025
Conventional practices	Low intensity	25.7	26.3
	High intensity	24.2	27.2
New CSF practices	Close-to-nature	10.7	33.5
	Natural dynamics	24.9	34.0
Control		32.2	30.0

Soil moisture. The water content of the soil is measured by installing a humidity sensor (TOMST sensors), on in each monitoring subplot (three per treatment). Due to delays in procuring the sensors, the installation of the sensors was completed in March 2025.

Table 12 and Figure 1 show the soil moisture values per treatment. The low-intensity treatment exhibits significantly higher soil moisture than the other practices and a slightly higher value than the control area. However, the sensor in the natural dynamic treatment

shows some measurement problems, with negative mean values. Overall, soil moisture levels were very low in all the practices.

Table 12. Mean, minim and maximum soil moisture per day and treatment.

Practices	Treatment	Data available from	Soil moisture (m ³ /m ³)		
			Mean	Min.	Max.
Conventional practices	Low intensity	03/2025	0.08 ± 0.01	-0.06	0.33
	High intensity	03/2025	0.04 ± 0.00	-0.05	0.24
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature	03/2025	0.01 ± 0.00	-0.04	0.19
	Natural dynamics	03/2025	-0.02 ± 0.00	-0.06	0.17
Control		03/2025	0.07 ± 0.00	-0.05	0.24

Figure 1. Average soil moisture per day and treatment.

3.2.3. Measuring the restoration of other ecosystem services

The restoration of ecosystem services is quantified using two variables: biodiversity and wood provision.

Biodiversity. Biodiversity is estimated using the Potential Biodiversity Index (IBP), which includes six factors that can be influenced by forest management practices to enhance biodiversity (A: Tree species diversity, B: Vertical vegetation structure, C: Standing deadwood, D: Fallen deadwood, E: Large living trees, F: Trees with dendromicrohabitats, G: Open spaces with flowering vegetation), and three fixed contextual factors depend on natural and historical site conditions and cannot be directly modified by management: (H: Forest continuity, I: Presence of water bodies, J: Rocky features). Each factor can be scored 0, 1, 2 or 5, and the sum of these scores provides a total IBP score, with a maximum value of 50.

Table 13 shows the IBP values for 2024. The potential for biodiversity carrying capacity in Requesens was found to be medium-low (28-34% of the maximum 50 points) for almost all the treatments except for the natural dynamics treatment where the carrying capacity was medium (44%). The factors that contributed most to biodiversity in the new CSF practices were the mixed character of the holm oak alongside the presence of strawberry trees, maples, oaks and mountain ash. The presence of rocky features also contributed to biodiversity in all treatments. Factors requiring further improvement include dead wood, both standing and on the ground, and large living trees. Microhabitats are singularities of the trees that certain species require at certain stages of their life cycle (e.g. cavities or wounds). The most abundant features in Holm oaks were concavities, agglomerations of shoots or branches, deformations, tree cankers, and epiphytic plants, lichens and parasites.

Table 13. IBP values per treatment and for each factor in 2024.

Practice	Treatment	Management-modifiable elements							Fixed Contextual Factors			IBP total	IBP %	Biodiversity carrying capacity
		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J			
Conventional practices	Low intensity	2	2	0	0	0	2	2	2	0	5	15	30%	Medium-Low
	High intensity	2	2	1	1	0	2	2	2	0	2	14	28%	Medium-Low
New CSF practices	Close-to-nature	5	1	0	0	0	2	2	2	0	2	14	28%	Medium-Low
	Natural dynamics	5	2	1	0	0	5	2	2	0	5	22	44%	Medium
Control		2	2	1	1	0	2	2	2	0	5	17	34%	Medium-Low

Figure 2 illustrates the contribution of each factor to the IBP for each treatment. This graphical representation indicates which factors require an increase to improve biodiversity in these areas.

Figure 2. Contribution of each factor to the total punctuation in each treatment in 2024.

The IBP was measured again in the final inventory, but only in the CSF practices where the interventions took place. Thanks to an increase in vertical vegetation structure and fallen deadwood resulting from the close-to-nature intervention, and an increase in fallen deadwood resulting from the natural dynamic intervention, both practices have slightly improved the IBP (Table 14).

Table 14. IBP values per treatment and for each factor in 2025.

Practice	Treatment	Management-modifiable elements							Fixed Contextual Factors			IBP total	IBP %	Biodiversity carrying capacity
		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J			
New CSF practices	Close-to-nature	5	2	0	2	0	2	2	2	0	2	17	34%	Medium-Low
	Natural dynamics	5	2	1	1	0	5	2	2	0	5	23	46%	Medium-Low

Wood provision. This is assessed by quantifying aboveground biomass, using tree diameter at breast height (DBH). Biomass is estimated using species-specific allometric models (see Table 7), which enable the calculation of the total aerial biomass (tonnes per hectare) of trunks, bark, branches, and roots.

Total aerial biomass values are shown in Table 15. Biomass ranges from 100 to 174 t/ha. The effects of low- and high-intensity treatments, which result in lower biomass, are observed 10 years after intervention. The new CSF practices have a lower impact on biomass reduction.

Some reference values for total aerial biomass can be found in the Catalan Ecological and Forest Inventory (IEFC) for Forest Region III, which was developed by CREAL ([Inventari Ecològic i Forestal de Catalunya - IEFC](#)) in 1988–1989. This inventory provides total aerial biomass values for the Alt Empordà county, where Requesens is located, of around 54.7 t/ha. Data is also available at the species level: the total aerial biomass for holm oak ranges from 14.9 to 167.2 t/ha, with an average of 59.8 t/ha. The Requesens treatments hold higher values of total aerial biomass than the regional mean but are still within the range of values.

Table 15. Total aerial biomass in each practice and treatment, in 2024 and 2025.

Practice	Treatment	Total aerial biomass (tn/ha)					
		2024			2025		
		Other species	Holm oak	Total	Other species	Holm oak	Total
Conventional practices	Low intensity	10.8	105.4	116.2			
	High intensity	12.6	88.8	101.5			
New CSF practices	Close-to-nature	61.6	81.0	142.6	53.7	78.8	132.5
	Natural dynamics	30.0	144.1	174.1	30.0	137.1	167.1
Control		14.7	143.9	158.6			

3.2.4. Measuring the reduction in fire risk

Fire risk reduction is quantified using two variables: forest structure and forest fuel continuity.

Forest structure. This is monitored through various factors, including tree density, basal area, regeneration and canopy cover.

Table 16 shows the density of each treatment in 2024 and the CSF practices in 2025. These values reveal different insights. The initial density is much higher in areas where CSF practices are performed than in control or conventional practices, particularly with regard to species other than holm oak. Furthermore, the CSF interventions are slight, yet the final density remains higher than in conventional or control practices. Secondly, the effects of low- and high-intensity treatments are clearly evident 10 years after intervention, with notably lower density in the high-intensity treatment. Thirdly, the high density of associated species after the intervention in the CSF practices highlights one of primary objective of this type of management: to retain biodiversity as an important factor in increasing resilience to climate change. Finally, although the initial density makes it difficult to compare the treatments, density evolution will be compared within each treatment over time.

Similar to the total aerial biomass, some density reference values can be found in the Catalan Ecological and Forest Inventory (IEFC, Forest Region III). The mean density of Holm oak in Alt Empordà county is around 2,105 ft/ha, and ranges from 359 to 8,529 ft/ha. All treatments fall within this range and are close to the mean value.

Table 16. Density in each practice and treatment plots, in 2024 and 2025.

Practice	Treatment	Density (ft/ha)					
		2024			2025		
		Other species	Holm oak	Total	Other species	Holm oak	Total
Conventional practices	Low intensity	244	2,175	2,419			
	High intensity	244	1,178	1,422			
New CSF practices	Close-to-nature	1,337	1,974	3,310	1,019	1,814	2,833
	Natural dynamics	520	2,239	2,759	520	2,207	2,727
Control		308	1,974	2,281			

Table 17 shows the basal area of each treatment in 2024, as well as the CFS practices in 2025. In this case, the initial values are quite similar between the new CSF practices and the control plot, and much higher than the conventional practices. Once again, the effects of the low- and high-intensity treatments are clearly evident 10 years after the intervention, with a notably lower basal area. The reduction in basal area following the CSF practices is slight, with a reduced impact on associated species, thereby favouring biodiversity conservation.

Some reference values for basal area can be found in the Catalan Ecological and Forest Inventory (IEFC, Forest Region III). The mean basal area of holm oak in Alt Empordà

county is around 17.1 m²/ha and ranges from 4.3 to 45.0 m²/ha. The mean basal area for all species in Alt Empordà is around 18.4 m²/ha. The basal area values obtained in Requesens are higher than the reference value, possibly due to a lack of management in the area for around 80 years.

Table 17. Basal area in each practice and treatment plots, in 2024 and 2025.

Practice	Treatment	Basal area (m ² /ha)					
		2024			2025		
		Other species	Holm oak	Total	Other species	Holm oak	Total
Conventional practices	Low intensity	3.6	25.2	28.8			
	High intensity	4.4	20.1	24.5			
New CSF practices	Close-to-nature	17.1	19.9	37.0	14.8	19.2	34.0
	Natural dynamics	8.5	33.2	41.7	8.5	31.8	40.3
Control		4.4	32.5	37.0			

Table 18 shows the canopy cover of each treatment in 2024, as well as in the CFS practices in 2025. The values indicate high canopy cover, approaching completeness in the control and low-intensity treatments. The new CFS practices have only slightly modified the canopy cover to avoid an increase in scrubland due to greater sunlight exposure.

Table 18. Canopy cover in each practice and treatment plots, in 2024 and 2025.

Practice	Treatment	Canopy cover (%)	
		2024	2025
Conventional practices	Low intensity	92	
	High intensity	88	
New CSF practices	Close-to-nature	85	83
	Natural dynamics	82	82
Control		97	

Table 19 shows the regeneration in different strata in 2024. The results indicate a high density of regeneration in the form of seedlings (with a diameter at breast height of less than 2.5 cm) and saplings (with a diameter at breast height of less than 7.5 cm), with notable differences observed between the various treatments. For example, the values for the natural dynamic treatment are notably lower than those for the other treatments.

Some reference values for regeneration can be found in the Catalan Ecological and Forest Inventory (IEFC, Forest Region III). The mean regeneration of holm oak ranges from 0 to 69,766 ft/ha, with an average of around 18,204 ft/ha. All treatments fall within this range and are close to the mean value.

Table 19. Regeneration in each practice and treatment plots in 2024.

Practice	Treatment	Regeneration (ft/ha)				
		2024				
		H ³ <30 cm	0,30 m≤ H<1,30m	H>=1,30m		Total
D ³ <2,5 cm	D<7,5 cm					
Conventional practices	Low intensity	7,083	15,833	2,083	833	25,833
	High intensity	5,000	14,583	14,167	3,750	37,500
New CSF practices	Close-to-nature	13,750	1,667	2,083	833	18,333
	Natural dynamics	3,333	833	1,667	0	5,833
Control		20,417	417	0	833	21,667

Forest fuel continuity. This refers to the spatial distribution and height of the different strata of the fuel (aerial, ladder or surface cover), which directly affects the forest's vulnerability to fire risk due to fire propagation. Forest fuel continuity is monitored through the crown fire hazard and the understorey biovolume.

Crown fire hazard is determined by visually estimating the percentage of fuel cover (aerial, surface, and ladder fuels) and measuring the height of surface fuel and the distance between aerial, surface, and ladder fuels. Using this data, a forest fuel continuity model can be estimated, which is related to a level of crown fire hazard: Low, Moderate or High.

Table 20 shows the fuel continuity model and the crown fire hazard for the treatments in 2024 and 2025. Compared with the other practices, conventional practices exhibited a high hazard. This is due to various factors: in the low-intensity treatment, logging residues remained after the intervention, creating vertical continuity between the combustible layers (superficial, ladder and aerial), consequently resulting in a high crown fire hazard. In the high-intensity treatment, opening the crown cover resulted in more light reaching the soil, facilitating understorey explosions and increasing the superficial and ladder fuel layers notably. The new CSF practices are surprising in that the crown fire hazard changed from low to moderate after the treatments. For close-to-nature silviculture, this can be explained by an increase in logging residues after the intervention, which is expected to change in the future. However, the natural dynamic treatment is expected to maintain a low hazard level in future, since the intervention did not affect fuel continuity. Longer monitoring is needed to draw conclusions about changes in crown fire hazard.

³ Ht is the total height, D is the diameter at breast height (1.3 m).

Table 20. Forest fuel continuity model and crown fire hazard in 2024 and 2025.

Practice	Treatment	2024		2025	
		Forest fuel continuity model	Crown fire hazard	Forest fuel continuity model	Crown fire hazard
Conventional practices	Low intensity	A3-A4	High	A2-A3-A4	High
	High intensity	A3	High	A3	High
New CSF practices	Close-to-nature	C14	Low	B14	Moderate
	Natural dynamics	C14-C17	Low	B14	Moderate
Control		A1-A3-B14	High-Moderate	B9-B14	Moderate

Figure 3. Graphic representation of the forest fuel continuity models present in Requesens (Source: (Piqué, et al., 2011)).

Understorey biovolume is estimated through 10-metre transects, where the vegetation cover and mean height are recorded. Multiplying these values together results in the biovolume of the understorey layer.

Table 21 shows that the effects of low- and high-intensity conventional practices are still evident 10 years after implementation. The understorey has grown strongly thanks to a higher light arrival, particularly in the high-intensity treatment.

Table 21. Understorey biovolume in each practice and treatment plots.

Practice	Treatment	Biovolume 2024 (m ³ /ha)
Conventional silvicultural practices	Low intensity	2,375.3
	High intensity	6,048.6
New CSF practices	Close-to-nature	372.7
	Natural dynamics	259.5
Control		1,323.2

4. Mixed forest of *Pinus sylvestris* and oaks in the Montesquiú natural park (Barcelona)

This chapter evaluates the performance of the practices implemented in the mixed forest of *Pinus sylvestris* and oaks in Montesquiú natural park. This evaluation uses **three different datasets**:

- The forests inventories developed in LIFE MIDMACC project, between 2014 and 2018. The inventory followed the criteria established in the monitoring protocol contained in (Savé, et al., 2015)
- The initial inventory of MONIMED project, performed in Autumn 2024 to capture the initial condition of the site. The inventory followed the indications and criteria set in the Monitoring protocol (Pascual, et al., 2025b).
- The final inventory of MONIMED project, performed in Autumn 2025 to evaluate the implemented practices. The inventory followed the indications and criteria set in the Monitoring protocol (Pascual, et al., 2025b).

Similarly to the previous location, **two different analyses have been performed**: the evaluation of the new Climate-Smart Forestry practices and the comparison of the practices using new monitoring parameters. All the results in this deliverable are shown per treatment, that's mean, that the values presented are the mean value of the three permanent circular subplots per treatment.

4.1. Evaluation of the new Climate-Smart Forestry practices

Two new Climate-Smart Forestry practices were implemented in December 2024 and January 2025 with the MONIMED project. The intensity of the interventions is estimated with the forest inventories developed on Autumn 2024 and 2025.

- **Close-to-Nature Silviculture Plot**: Application of the individual-tree silvicultural method, where high-quality trees for multiple objectives (biodiversity conservation, timber production, and natural regeneration) were selected. The intensity of the practice was:
 - A 28%-reduction in basal area and a 26%-reduction in density.
- **Plot of preparation to natural dynamics** in non-productive stands: Application of concrete interventions to promote forest maturity and restore complex ecological processes by minimizing human influence. The intensity of the practice was:
 - An 8%-reduction in basal area and a 4%-reduction in density.

Table 22 summarises the initial density and basal area of each treatment area, the figures following the implementation of forest management, and the percentage change. In this case, the new close-to-nature treatment is more intense than the low- and high-intensity treatments, mainly because the starting point of the new practice area has a notably higher basal area than the others due to the larger size of the trees, and a more

intense cut is needed to reduce competition. Following the treatments, the density values are more similar across the five practices, although the control plots exhibit higher density. The two control areas differ significantly, particularly in terms of basal area, indicating that a second control area was necessary for comparison with the new CSF practices.

Table 22. Summary of the density and basal area per treatment, before the forest management, after the management and percentage of change.

Practices	Treatment	Density			Basal area		
		Pre-treatment (ft/ha)	Post-treatment (ft/ha)	Change (%)	Pre-treatment (m ² /ha)	Post-treatment (m ² /ha)	Change (%)
Conventional practices (2015)	Low intensity	944	785	-17%	28.7	27.4	-4%
	High intensity	1,125	859	-24%	32.9	27.2	-17%
	Pine logging	1,899	690	-64%	40.9	10.2	-75%
New CSF practices (2024-2025)	Close-to-nature	966	716	-26%	35.1	25.2	-28%
	Natural dynamics	764	732	-4%	38.9	36.0	-8%
Control (2015)		1,061	1,061	-	29.0	29.0	-
Control2 (2025)		971	971	-	39.1	39.1	-

4.2. Evaluation of the practices using new monitoring parameters

All the practices are evaluated using the monitoring parameters established in the monitoring protocol (Pascual, et al., 2025b). For this evaluation, the dataset of the initial inventory of MONIMED project (Autumn 2024) is used for all the practices. Moreover, the results of the final inventory of the MONIMED project (Autumn 2025) are shown in the two new practices, to capture the final situation of the forest after the new treatments.

4.2.1. Measuring the mitigation capacity

Carbon storage in soils. The carbon content of the topsoil and litter is estimated (MgC/ha). Table 23 shows the carbon content of the soil and litter, after the sampling in 2024. Total carbon stocks range from 32 to 67 tonnes of carbon per hectare. Some variability is observed among the sites, particularly in the conventional practices, where total carbon stocks double those in pine-logging compared with high-intensity treatment. The organic content of the soil and litter will be measured again in three years' time, by which point some initial changes and trends among the practices may have become apparent.

Table 23. Soil, litter and total carbon content in each treatment in 2024.

Practice	Treatment	Soil organic content (SOC, MgC/ha)	Litter organic content (MgC/ha)	Total carbon stocks (MgC/ha)
Conventional practices	Low intensity	65.6	1.8	67.4
	High intensity	55.1	2.4	57.5
	Pine logging	30.5	1.5	32.0
New CSF practices	Close-to-nature	44.7	2.3	47.1
	Natural dynamics	43.4	1.7	45.1
Control		47.9	1.8	49.7
Control2		57.0	2.1	59.1

Carbon storage in forests. The species-specific allometric models shown in Table 7 are used to estimate aboveground biomass in trunks, bark, branches and roots. Aerial carbon stocks are then estimated by dividing the aboveground biomass by 2.1 (approximately half). Table 24 shows the aerial carbon stocks in each treatment plot. The values oscillate between 31 and 70.6 t/ha. There is a difference between the first sites, where low- and high-intensity treatments were located, and the new sites where CSF practices are implemented. In the latter, the contribution of pine to the aerial carbon stock is significant. In contrast, in the new sites where CSF practices have been implemented, other species, mainly beeches with a high diameter, make a significant contribution to carbon stocks.

Table 24. Aerial carbon stock in each practice and treatment, in 2024 and 2025.

Practices	Treatment	Aerial carbon stock (MgC/ha)							
		2024				2025			
		Other species	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	Oaks	Total	Other species	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	Oaks	Total
Conventional practices	Low intensity	2.5	38.9	4.3	45.7				
	High intensity	0.5	42.2	0.1	42.9				
	Pine logging	2.2	0.0	29.1	31.3				
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature	11.9	33.4	7.8	53.0	6.6	24.9	7.4	38.9
	Natural dynamics	39.8	27.5	3.4	70.6	39.8	22.4	3.4	65.5
Control		0.2	29.6	21.4	51.2				
Control2		9.7	43.5	3.1	56.4				

Understorey carbon stock was estimated through 10-metre transects and using the biovolume-based allometric models shown in Table 9. Table 25 shows the understorey carbon stock in each treatment. These values are very similar across the majority of the treatments and are very low, ranging from 2.3 to 4.8 MgC/ha. The only exception is the high-intensity treatment, where the carbon stock is double that of the other treatments, mainly due to the opening of the canopy cover stimulating understorey resprouting.

Table 25. Understory carbon stock in each practice and treatment.

Practices	Treatment	Understory carbon stock (MgC/ha)
		2024
Conventional practices	Low intensity	4.8
	High intensity	8.4 ⁴
	Pine logging	4.2
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature	2.3
	Natural dynamics	2.9
Control		4.4
Control2		2.7

4.2.2. Measuring the resistance to droughts

Forest health status. Table 26 shows the forest decay in 2024 and 2025. It also includes LIFE MEDACC decline values from 2015 to 2020. During the LIFE MEDACC monitoring period, the influence of forest management on resistance to forest decline can be observed, whereas forest decline remains constant in conventional practices and grows exponentially in the control area. However, the situation changes in 2024, mainly due to the strong impact of a long-term drought affecting the area from 2022 to 2025. Almost all treatments show half of the pine crowns to be decolorised or defoliated, and no positive effects of forest management are observed except in the pine logging treatment. In this case, the crowns evaluated are oak, rather than pine, and oak seems to be more resilient to drought than pine in Montesquiú, mainly because the *Pinus sylvestris* is at the limit of its geographical distribution and is suffering the effects of climate change more severely than other species in the area.

In 2025, forest decline decreased in almost all treatments, similarly to the Requesens forest. This appears to have been caused by human error in the visual estimation, as the field team was different for the final inventory. This analysis will be performed again in 2028, when more evident effects are expected.

⁴ In the high-intensity treatment, the transects were only measured in one of the monitoring subplots due to the difficulty of accessing the others, as these areas were covered in scrubland, brambles and prickly plants.

Table 26. Percentage of forest decline in Montesquiu.

Practices	Treatment	Forest decline (%)						
		2015	2016	2017	2019	2020	2024	2025
Conventional practices	Low intensity	23.9	21.3	11.5	21.1	29.4	56.9	55.2
	High intensity	14.5	27.1	13.8	11.0	20.2	43.5	52.8
	Pine logging						24.3 ⁵	22.5 ⁴
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature						60.2	42.0
	Natural dynamics						52.6	33.9
Control		15.0	19.7	31.0	34.0	48.0	49.8	45.3
Control2							56.0	36.5

Soil moisture. The water content of the soil is measured by installing a humidity sensor (TOMST sensors), on in each monitoring subplot (three per treatment). Due to delays in procuring the sensors, the installation of the sensors was completed in March 2025.

Table 27 and Figure 4 show the soil moisture values per treatment. All the treatments exhibit a similar soil moisture, higher in the high intensity and control treatments, and lower in the low intensity and natural dynamics, but the differences are not yet significant. A longer data series is needed to draw more robust conclusions.

Table 27. Mean, minim and maximum soil moisture per day and treatment.

Practices	Treatment	Data available from	Soil moisture (m ³ /m ³)		
			Mean	Min.	Max.
Conventional practices	Low intensity	03/2025	0.14 ± 0.00	-0.07	0.27
	High intensity	03/2025	0.19 ± 0.01	-0.13	0.35
	Pine logging	03/2025	0.15 ± 0.01	-0.07	0.33
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature	03/2025	0.16 ± 0.00	-0.05	0.29
	Natural dynamics	03/2025	0.14 ± 0.00	-0.04	0.25
Control		05/2025	0.19 ± 0.01	-0.06	0.35

⁵ In the case of pine logging, the percentage of defoliated and discoloured crown is measured on oaks, as there are no pines remaining in the plot.

Figure 4. Average soil moisture per day and treatment.

4.2.3. Measuring the restoration of other ecosystem services

Biodiversity. Table 28 shows the IBP values for 2024. The potential for biodiversity carrying capacity in Montesquiú was found to be medium-low (34-48%) across all the treatments. The factor that contributed most to biodiversity in all practices was the mixed character of the Scots pine alongside beeches, oaks, maples, mountain ash, common hawthorn or holm oaks. Further improvement is required in terms of vertical vegetation structure, standing and fallen deadwood, large living trees and open spaces with flowering vegetation.

Table 28. IBP values per treatment and for each factor in 2024.

Practices	Treatment	Management-modifiable elements						Fixed Contextual Factors			IBP total	IBP %	Biodiversity carrying capacity	
		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I				J
Conventional practices	Low intensity	5	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	0	19	38%	Medium-Low
	High intensity	5	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	0	18	36%	Medium-Low
	Pine logging	5	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	0	0	17	34%	Medium-Low
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature	5	1	1	2	1	2	0	5	0	0	17	34%	Medium-Low
	Natural dynamics	5	1	5	5	2	2	0	2	0	2	24	48%	Medium
Control		5	2	2	2	1	1	0	2	0	2	17	34%	Medium-Low
Control2		5	1	1	2	1	2	0	5	0	5	22	44%	Medium

Figure 5 illustrates the contribution of each factor to the IBP for each treatment. This graphical representation indicates which factors require an increase to improve biodiversity in these areas.

Figure 5. Contribution of each factor to the total punctuation in each treatment in 2024

The IBP was measured again during the final inventory, but only in the CSF practices where the interventions took place. Thanks to an improvement in the vertical vegetation structure, standing deadwood, and trees with dendromicrohabitats as a consequence of the action, both treatments have slightly increased the IBP (Table 29).

Table 29. IBP values per treatment and for each factor in 2025.

Practices	Treatment	Management-modifiable elements							Fixed Contextual Factors			IBP total	IBP %	Biodiversity carrying capacity
		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J			
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature	5	2	2	2	1	2	0	5	0	0	19	38%	Medium-Low
	Natural dynamics	5	2	5	5	2	5	0	2	0	2	28	56%	Medium

Wood provision. This is assessed by quantifying aboveground biomass, using the diameter of trees at breast height (DBH). Total aerial biomass values are shown in Table 30. Biomass ranges from 65.8 to 148 tonnes per hectare. The effects of the conventional practices are still evident, particularly in pine logging, where all the pines were removed. The area where the new CSF practices and the new control2 differ from the previous ones in that they have a higher total aerial biomass, which remains high after treatment in the natural dynamic' treatment.

Some reference values for total aerial biomass can be found in the Catalan Ecological and Forest Inventory (IEFC) for Forest Region II, which was developed by CREAL ([Inventari Ecològic i Forestal de Catalunya - IEFC](#)) in 1988–1989. This inventory provides total aerial biomass values for the Osona county, where Montesquiú is located, of around 66.7 t/ha. Data is also available at the species level: the total aerial biomass for Scots pine ranges from 15.1 to 278.3 t/ha, with an average of 73.4 t/ha. The Montesquiú treatments exhibit higher values of total aerial biomass than the regional mean but remain within the expected range. The natural dynamic' treatment exhibits notable values for other species, mainly due to the presence of large trees, primarily beeches, with a high diameter.

Table 30. Total aerial biomass in each practice and treatment, in 2024 and 2025.

Practices	Treatment	Total aerial biomass (tn/ha)							
		2024				2025			
		Other species	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	Oaks	Total	Other species	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	Oaks	Total
Conventional practices	Low intensity	5.3	81.7	9.0	96.1				
	High intensity	1.0	88.7	0.3	90.0				
	Pine logging	4.6	0.0	61.1	65.8				
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature	24.9	70.2	16.3	111.4	13.9	52.2	15.6	81.7
	Natural dynamics	83.5	57.7	7.1	148.2	83.5	47.0	7.1	137.5
Control		0.4	62.2	44.9	107.4				
Control2		20.4	91.3	6.6	118.3				

4.2.4. Measuring the reduction of fire risk

Forest structure. This is monitored through various factors, including tree density, basal area, regeneration and canopy cover.

Table 31 shows the density of each treatment in 2024, alongside the CSF practices in 2025. The density in 2024 is quite similar for all treatments, at around 800–900 ft/ha. However, there is an anomalous value in the high-intensity treatment that does not coincide with the expected density. This may be an error, as two of the three permanent monitoring subplots of this treatment were completely covered by bushes and prickly plants, making access difficult. It is therefore suspected that not all the trees were surveyed, resulting in an unexpectedly low-density value. Furthermore, following the CSF interventions, the final density is relatively lower than that of conventional practices.

As with the total aerial biomass, some density reference values can be found in the Catalan Ecological and Forest Inventory (IEFC, Forest Region II). The mean density of Scots pine in the Osona county is around 1,028 ft/ha, and ranges from 214 to 4,317 ft/ha. All treatments exhibit a lower density than the mean value, reflecting the effect of recent forest management practices in the area.

Table 31. Density in each practice and treatment plots, in 2024 and 2025.

Practices	Treatment	Density (ft/ha)							
		2024				2025			
		Other species	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	Oaks	Total	Other species	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	Oaks	Total
Conventional practices	Low intensity	159	531	117	806				
	High intensity	11	446	11	467 ⁶				
	Pine logging	127	0	806	934				
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature	499	350	117	966	382	223	111	716
	Natural dynamics	541	175	48	764	541	143	48	732
Control		32	414	467	912				
Control2		366	525	80	971				

Table 32 shows the basal area of each treatment in 2024, as well as the CSF practices in 2025. The basal area is much higher in the area where new CSF practices and Control 2 exist due to the presence of large trees. Following the CSF interventions, the final basal area remains relatively consistent across the conventional practices and the close-to-nature treatment but remains quite high in the natural dynamics' treatment.

Reference values for basal area can be found in the Catalan Ecological and Forest Inventory (IEFC, Forest Region II). The mean Scots pine basal area in the Osona county is around 23.3 m²/ha, ranging from 7.64 to 77.8 m²/ha. The mean basal area for all

⁶ In the high-intensity treatment, two of the three permanent monitoring subplots were completely covered by bushes and prickly plants, which made access difficult. For this reason, it is suspected that not all the trees were surveyed, resulting in an unexpectedly low-density value.

species in Osona is around 18.1 m²/ha. The basal area values obtained in Montesquiu are higher than the reference values.

Table 32. Basal area in each practice and treatment plots, in 2024 and 2025.

Practices	Treatment	Basal area (m ² /ha)							
		2024				2025			
		Other species	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	Oaks	Total	Other species	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	Oaks	Total
Conventional practices	Low intensity	2.5	24.9	2.2	29.6				
	High intensity	0.5	26.0	0.1	26.6				
	Pine logging	2.0	0.0	15.1	17.1				
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature	10.6	20.8	3.7	35.1	6.5	15.1	3.6	25.2
	Natural dynamics	21.3	16.0	1.7	38.9	21.3	13.0	1.7	36.0
Control		0.2	18.4	10.9	29.5				
Control2		10.1	27.4	1.6	39.1				

Table 33 shows the canopy cover of each treatment in 2024, as well as in the CFS practices in 2025. The values indicate high canopy cover in almost all treatments. The high values in 2025 suggest an error in the visual estimation of canopy cover, as the percentage should have decreased slightly following treatment.

Table 33. Canopy cover in each practice and treatment plots, in 2024 and 2025.

Practices	Treatment	Canopy cover (%)	
		2024	2025
Conventional practices	Low intensity	70	
	High intensity	95	
	Pine logging	88	
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature	70	83
	Natural dynamics	88	99
Control		92	
Control2		85	

Table 34 shows the regeneration in different strata in 2024. The results indicate a high density of regeneration mainly in the form of seedlings (with a diameter at breast height of less than 2.5 cm), while the regeneration of saplings (with a diameter at breast height of less than 7.5 cm) is notably lower. Notable differences are observed between the various treatments. For instance, in the pine logging treatment, the regeneration of oaks, maples and holm oaks has exploded due to the highly open canopy resulting from the removal of pines. In conventional practices, regeneration in 2024 was quite high, possibly due to the 2015 management intervention that allowed sunlight to reach the ground. Meanwhile, regeneration in the new CSF practices is almost non-existent, implying the need to open the canopy to accelerate regeneration. It should be noted that the dominant species in the regeneration are oak, holly, common hawthorn, maple, holm oak and common box, in that order, but there is no regeneration of Scots pine.

Some reference values for regeneration can be found in the Catalan Ecological and Forest Inventory (IEFC, Forest Region II). The mean regeneration of Scots pine under Scots pine forest ranges from 0 to 13,905 ft/ha, with an average of around 1,353 ft/ha. The regeneration of oaks (*Quercus humilis*) under Scots pine is about 6,544 ft/ha and of holm oak (*Quercus ilex*) is about 6,664 ft/ha. All treatments exhibit a larger regeneration than expected.

Table 34. Regeneration in each practice and treatment plots in 2024.

Practices	Treatment	Resprouting (ft/ha)				
		2024				
		Ht<30 cm	0,30 m≤ Ht<1,30m	Ht≥1,30m		Total
		Dn<2,5 cm	Dn<7,5 cm			
Conventional practices	Low intensity	12,500	6,667	4,583	417	24,167
	High intensity	6,667	10,833	5,417	833	23,750
	Pine logging	45,417	9,167	4,167	833	59,583
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature	1,250	0	2,083	833	4,167
	Natural dynamics	3,438	0	938	1,875	6,250
Control		17,917	7,083	3,750	2,917	31,667
Control2		8,750	4,375	0	1,250	14,375

Forest fuel continuity. Table 35 illustrates the fuel continuity model and the crown fire hazard associated with the treatments in 2024 and 2025. A different pattern is observed between the old and new sites. In the area where conventional practices were applied in 2015, the crown fire hazard is high, which is consistent with the increase in understorey biomass and regeneration. In the area where new CSF practices were applied in 2024, the crown fire hazard is low before and after the treatment, primarily due to the stand's more humid and northerly orientation, which has enabled the growth of larger trees and reduced understorey presence. Longer monitoring is needed to draw conclusions about changes in crown fire hazard.

Table 35. Forest fuel continuity model and crown fire hazard in 2024 and 2025.

Practice	Treatment	2024		2025	
		Forest fuel continuity model	Crown fire hazard	Forest fuel continuity model	Crown fire hazard
Conventional practices	Low intensity	A3-A4	High	A3-A4-B8	High – Moderate
	High intensity	A2	High	A4-B8	High – Moderate
	Pine logging	A2-A4	High	A4-B8	High – Moderate
New CSF practices	Close-to-nature	C12	Low	C12	Low
	Natural dynamics	C12	Low	C12	Low
Control		A1-A2	High	A4	High
Control2		C12	Low	B2-C12	Moderate - Low

Figure 6. Graphic representation of the forest fuel continuity models present in Montesquiu (Source: (Piqué, et al., 2011)).

Table 36 shows the understorey biovolume in Montesquiu. The effects of conventional practices are still evident 10 years after implementation, particularly in the high-intensity treatment. Here, the biovolume is six times higher than that of in the other treatments, primarily because opening the canopy cover stimulates understorey resprouting.

Table 36. Understorey biovolume in each practice and treatment plots.

Practices	Treatment	Biovolume 2024 (m ³ /ha)
Conventional practices	Low intensity	2,290.0
	High intensity	11,856.0 ⁷
	Pine logging	2,229.8
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature	344.9
	Natural dynamics	2,049.2
Control		1,591.8
Control2		554.1

⁷ In the high-intensity treatment, the transects were only measured in one of the monitoring subplots due to the difficulty of accessing the others, as these areas were covered in scrubland, brambles and prickly plants.

5. Holm oak forest in the Montnegre-Corredor natural park (Barcelona)

This chapter evaluates the performance of the practices implemented in the Holm oak forest in Montnegre-Corredor natural park. This evaluation uses **three different datasets**:

- The forests inventories developed in SUDOE MONTCLIMA project (<https://www.montclima.eu/en>), between 2020 and 2023. The inventory followed the criteria established in the monitoring protocol contained in (Guitart , et al., 2022).
- The initial inventory of MONIMED project, performed in Autumn 2024 to capture the initial condition of the site. The inventory followed the indications and criteria set in the Monitoring protocol (Pascual, et al., 2025b).
- The final inventory of MONIMED project, performed in Autumn 2025 to evaluate the implemented practices. The inventory followed the indications and criteria set in the Monitoring protocol (Pascual, et al., 2025b).

Similarly to the previous locations, **two different analyses have been performed**: the evaluation of the new Climate-Smart Forestry practices and the comparison of the practices using new monitoring parameters. All the results in this deliverable are shown per treatment, that's mean, that the values presented are the mean value of the three permanent circular subplots per treatment.

5.1. Evaluation of the new Climate-Smart Forestry practices

Two new Climate-Smart Forestry practices were implemented in December 2024 and January 2025 with the MONIMED project. The intensity of the interventions is estimated with the forest inventories developed on Autumn 2024 and 2025.

- **Close-to-Nature Silviculture Plot**: Application of the individual-tree silvicultural method, where high-quality trees for multiple objectives (biodiversity conservation, timber production, and natural regeneration) were selected. The intensity of the practice was:
 - A 16%-reduction in basal area and a 36%-reduction in density.
 - A 22%-reduction in canopy cover.
- **Plot of preparation to natural dynamics** in non-productive stands: Application of concrete interventions to promote forest maturity and restore complex ecological processes by minimizing human influence. The intensity of the practice was:
 - A 6%-reduction in basal area and a 2%-reduction in density.
 - No changes in the canopy cover.

Table 37 summarises the initial density and basal area of each treatment area, the numbers after forest management was implemented, and the percentage change. In this

case, the intensity of the new close-to-nature treatment is higher than the conventional practice, which was not the expected outcome. This fact is caused because the initial situation of the forest in the pre-treatment inventory was very different between the sites. While the initial density was 1,075 ft/ha in the conventional practice, the close-to-nature forest had a density that was 61% higher (1,729 ft/ha). For this reason, the treatment required a greater reduction in density to achieve a similar density. The same is evident with the basal area, although the final basal area in the close-to-nature treatment reflect the necessity of a new thinning soon. By 2025, density values were more similar among the sites.

Table 37. Summary of the density and basal area per treatment, before the forest management, after the management and percentage of change.

Practices	Treatment	Density			Basal area		
		Pre-treatment (ft/ha)	Post-treatment (ft/ha)	Change (%)	Pre-treatment (m ² /ha)	Post-treatment (m ² /ha)	Change (%)
Conventional practices (2020)	Irregular forest management model	1,075	872	19%	23.1	21.4	8%
New CSF practices (2024-2025)	Close-to-nature	1,729	1,114	36%	35.6	29.8	16%
	Natural dynamics	1,369	1,337	2%	25.1	23.6	6%
Control		1,199	1,199	-	29.0	29.0	-

5.2. Evaluation of the practices using new monitoring parameters

All the practices are evaluated using the monitoring parameters established in the monitoring protocol (Pascual, et al., 2025b). For this evaluation, the dataset of the initial inventory of MONIMED project (Autumn 2024) is used for all the practices. Moreover, the results of the final inventory of the MONIMED project (Autumn 2025) are shown in the two new practices, to capture the final situation of the forest after the new treatments.

5.2.1. Measuring the mitigation capacity

Carbon storage in soils. The carbon content of the topsoil and litter is estimated (MgC/ha). Table 38 shows the carbon content of the soil and litter, after the sampling in 2024. Total carbon stocks are very similar in all treatments and oscillate between 28 and 36 tonnes of carbon per hectare. The organic content of the soil and litter will be measured again in three years' time, by which point some initial changes and trends among the practices may have become apparent.

Table 38. Soil, litter and total carbon content in each treatment in 2024.

Practice	Treatment	Soil organic content (SOC, MgC/ha)	Litter organic content (MgC/ha)	Total carbon stocks (MgC/ha)
Conventional practices	Irregular forest management	33.2	3.4	36.6
New CSF practices	Close-to-nature	26.2	6.9	33.1
	Natural dynamics	32.4	3.6	36.0
Control		24.0	4.0	28.0

Carbon storage in forests. The species-specific allometric models shown in Table 7 are used to estimate aboveground biomass in trunks, bark, branches and roots. Aerial carbon stocks are then estimated by dividing the aboveground biomass by 2.1 (approximately half). Table 39 shows the aerial carbon stocks in each treatment plot. The values oscillate between 48 and 73 MgC/ha. There is a difference between the first sites where conventional practices and controls were located, where the weight of the holm oak's contribution to the aerial carbon stock is similar to that of other species. In contrast, in the new sites where CSF practices are implemented, the holm oak's contribution is 4–5 times greater than that of other species.

Table 39. Aerial carbon stock in each practice and treatment, in 2024 and 2025.

Practices	Treatment	Aerial carbon stock (MgC/ha)					
		2024			2025		
		Other species	Holm oak	Total	Other species	Holm oak	Total
Conventional practices	Irregular forest management	21.4	27.0	48.5			
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature	17.1	56.6	73.7	15.5	46.7	62.2
	Natural dynamics	11.4	39.5	50.9	10.0	38.1	48.1
Control		21.1	32.1	53.2			

Understory carbon stock is estimated through 10-metre transects and using the biovolume-based allometric models shown in Table 9. Table 40 shows the understorey carbon stock in each treatment. The values are very similar in all the treatments and very low, ranging from 1.9 to 2.5 MgC/ha.

Table 40. Understorey carbon stock in each practice and treatment.

Practices	Treatment	Understorey carbon stock (MgC/ha)
		2024
Conventional practices	Irregular forest management	2.4
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature	2.5
	Natural dynamics	2.2
Control		1.9

5.2.2. Measuring the resistance to droughts

Forest health status. Table 41 shows the forest decay in 2024 and 2025. It also includes the decline values of SUDOE MONTCLIMA in 2020, 2021 and 2022. A strong episode of the defoliator *Lymantria dispar* caused a notable decline in 2020, which was exacerbated by a severe drought in 2021 and 2022. By 2024, the forest had begun to recover slightly from the decay. However, the rate of forest decline slowed significantly in 2025, which is important because forests cannot recover that quickly. This seems to have been caused by a human error in the visual estimation, since the field team changed for the final inventory. This analysis will be performed again in 2028, when more evident effects are expected.

Table 41. Percentage of forest decline in 2024 and 2025.

Practices	Treatment	Forest decline (%)				
		2020	2021	2022	2024	2025
Conventional practices	Irregular forest management	31.2	44.7	51.6	43.3	27.2
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature				36.0	28.3
	Natural dynamics				38.0	36.5
Control		33.5	50.0	67.3	52.0	26.5

Soil moisture. The water content of the soil is measured by installing a humidity sensor, on in each monitoring subplot (three per treatment). Different sensors are used for the various treatments. HOBO sensors were installed in the conventional practice and control plots as part of the SUDOE MONTCLIMA project, while TOMST sensors were used for the new CSF practices.

The installation of the TOMST sensors was completed in March 2025 due to delays in procuring the sensors. Once installed, however, wild pigs in the natural dynamics' treatment area caused problems by digging up the sensors, meaning the data collected was invalid for analysis. Additionally, the HOBO sensors installed in 2020 had no power and had to be restarted in May 2025. Consequently, soil moisture data is only available from May or June 2025 onwards, with no data available for the natural dynamics' treatment.

Table 42 and Figure 7 show the soil moisture values per treatment. The close-to-nature treatment exhibits significantly higher soil moisture than the control and conventional practices, whereas the control plot has significantly higher soil moisture than the conventional practice. A longer data series is needed to draw more robust conclusions.

Table 42. Mean, minim and maximum soil moisture per day and treatment.

Practices	Treatment	Sensor	Data available from	Soil moisture (m ³ /m ³)		
				Mean	Min.	Max.
Conventional practices	Irregular forest management	HOBO	06/2025	0.003±0.001	-0.010	0.070
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature	TOMST	05/2025	0.072±0.002	0.031	0.160
	Natural dynamics	TOMST	-	-	-	-
Control		HOBO	05/2025	0.038±0.002	-0.020	0.150

Figure 7. Average soil moisture per day and treatment.

5.2.3. Measuring the restoration of other ecosystem services

Biodiversity. Table 43 shows the IBP values for 2024. The potential for biodiversity carrying capacity in Montnegre-Corredor was found to be medium (44-52%) across all the treatments. The factors that contributed most to biodiversity in all practices were the mixed character of the holm oak alongside pines, oaks, strawberry trees, common hawthorn and mountain ash; standing deadwood; the trees with dendromicrohabitats. Further improvement is required in terms of large living trees in the close-to-nature practice and fallen deadwood in the control area.

Table 43. IBP values per treatment and for each factor in 2024.

Practices	Treatment	Management-modifiable elements							Fixed Contextual Factors			IBP total	IBP %	Biodiversity carrying capacity
		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J			
Conventional practices	Irregular management	5	2	2	2	2	5	2	2	0	0	22	44%	Medium
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature	5	2	5	2	1	5	2	2	0	2	26	52%	Medium
	Natural dynamics	5	2	5	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	24	48%	Medium
Control		5	2	5	0	2	5	2	2	0	0	23	46%	Medium

Figure 8 illustrates the contribution of each factor to the IBP for each treatment. This graphical representation indicates which factors require an increase to improve biodiversity in these areas.

Figure 8. Contribution of each factor to the total punctuation in each treatment in 2024.

The IBP was measured again during the final inventory, but only in the CSF practices where the interventions took place. Thanks to an increase in fallen deadwood as a consequence of the action, both treatments have slightly increased the IBP (Table 44).

Table 44. IBP values per treatment and for each factor in 2025.

Practices	Treatment	Management-modifiable elements							Fixed Contextual Factors			IBP total	IBP %	Biodiversity carrying capacity
		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J			
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature	5	2	5	5	1	5	2	2	0	2	29	58%	Medium
	Natural dynamics	5	2	5	5	2	2	2	2	2	0	27	54%	Medium

Wood provision. This is assessed by quantifying aboveground biomass, using tree diameter at breast height (DBH). Total aerial biomass values are shown in Table 45. Biomass ranges from 101 to 155 t/ha. Following the implementation of the new CSF practices, the total aerial biomass was homogenised across all treatments except the close-to-nature treatment.

Some reference values for total aerial biomass can be found in the Catalan Ecological and Forest Inventory (IEFC) for Forest Region V, which was developed by CREAM ([Inventari Ecològic i Forestal de Catalunya - IEFC](#)) in 1988–1989. This inventory provides total aerial biomass values for the Maresme county, where Montnegre-Corridor is located, of around 76.1 t/ha. Data is also available at the species level: the total aerial biomass for holm oak ranges from 13.1 to 254.4 t/ha, with an average of 73.6 t/ha. The Montnegre treatments hold higher values of total aerial biomass than the regional mean, but are still within the range of values.

Table 45. Total aerial biomass in each practice and treatment, in 2024 and 2025.

Practice	Treatment	Total aerial biomass (tn/ha)					
		2024			2025		
		Other species	Holm oak	Total	Other species	Holm oak	Total
Conventional practices	Irregular forest management	45.0	56.8	101.8			
New CSF practices	Close-to-nature	36.0	118.8	154.8	32.7	98.0	130.7
	Natural dynamics	23.9	83.0	106.9	21.1	80.0	101.1
Control		44.3	67.4	111.7			

5.2.4. Measuring the reduction of fire risk

Forest structure. This is monitored through various factors, including tree density, basal area, regeneration and canopy cover.

Table 46 shows the density of each treatment in 2024, alongside the CSF practices in 2025. The initial density is higher in the close-to-nature treatment, particularly with regard to holm oak density. Following the CSF interventions, the final density is relatively consistent across the treatments, ranging from 1,050 to 1,337 ft/ha. Given a similar initial density, its evolution will be compared within each treatment over time.

As with the total aerial biomass, some density reference values can be found in the Catalan Ecological and Forest Inventory (IEFC, Forest Region V). The mean density of holm oak in the Montnegre county is around 1,744 ft/ha, and ranges from 466 to 5,280 ft/ha. All treatments exhibit a lower density than the mean value, reflecting the effect of recent forest management practices in the area.

Table 46. Density in each practice and treatment plots, in 2024 and 2025.

Practices	Treatment	Density (ft/ha)					
		2024			2025		
		Other species	Holm oak	Total	Other species	Holm oak	Total
Conventional practices	Irregular forest management	382	668	1,050			
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature	361	1,369	1,729	202	912	1,114
	Natural dynamics	329	1,040	1,369	318	1,019	1,337
Control		435	711	1,146			

Table 47 shows the basal area of each treatment in 2024, as well as the CFS practices in 2025. As with density, the basal area is higher in the close-to-nature treatment, particularly with regard to holm oak. Following the CSF interventions, the final basal area remains relatively consistent across the treatments, ranging from 23.6 to 29.8 m²/ha.

Reference values for basal area can be found in the Catalan Ecological and Forest Inventory (IEFC, Forest Region V). The mean holm oak basal area in the Montnegre county is around 18.9 m²/ha, ranging from 5.4 to 56.7 m²/ha. The mean basal area for all species in Montnegre is around 22.7 m²/ha. The basal area values obtained in Montnegre are very similar to the reference values.

Table 47. Basal area in each practice and treatment plots, in 2024 and 2025.

Practices	Treatment	Basal area (m ² /ha)					
		2024			2025		
		Other species	Holm oak	Total	Other species	Holm oak	Total
Conventional practices	Irregular forest management	13.0	12.6	25.5			
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature	9.3	26.3	35.6	8.5	21.3	29.8
	Natural dynamics	6.6	18.5	25.1	5.7	17.8	23.6
Control		14.8	14.8	29.6			

Table 48 shows the canopy cover of each treatment in 2024, as well as in the CFS practices in 2025. The values indicate high canopy cover, approaching completeness in the control and low-intensity treatments. The new CFS practices have slightly modified the canopy cover to avoid an increase in scrubland due to greater sunlight exposure.

Table 48. Canopy cover in each practice and treatment plots, in 2024 and 2025.

Practices	Treatment	Canopy cover (%)	
		2024	2025
Conventional practices	Irregular forest management	88	
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature	85	67
	Natural dynamics	90	88
Control		90	

Table 49 shows the regeneration in different strata in 2024. The results indicate a high density of regeneration mainly in the form of seedlings (with a diameter at breast height of less than 2.5 cm), while the regeneration of saplings (with a diameter at breast height of less than 7.5 cm) is notably lower. Notable differences are observed between the various treatments. For example, the values for the natural dynamic treatment are notably lower than those for the other treatments, which may be explained by its location far from the other treatments in a less accessible area, with higher canopy cover and less sunlight reaching the regeneration.

Some reference values for regeneration can be found in the Catalan Ecological and Forest Inventory (IEFC, Forest Region V). The mean regeneration of holm oak ranges from 3,727 to 586,635 ft/ha, with an average of around 38,741 ft/ha. All treatments fall within this range and below the mean value.

Table 49. Regeneration in each practice and treatment plots in 2024.

Practices	Treatment	Resprouting (ft/ha)				
		2024				
		Ht<30 cm	0,30 m≤ Ht<1,30m	Ht≥1,30m		Total
		Dn<2,5 cm	Dn<7,5 cm			
Conventional practices	Irregular forest management	10,000	10,750	0	0	20,750
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature	10,000	21,250	2,917	0	34,167
	Natural dynamics	8,333	5,417	0	417	14,167
Control		9,167	20,417	1,250	1,250	32,083

Forest fuel continuity. Table 50 shows the fuel continuity model and the crown fire hazard for the treatments in 2024 and 2025. It also includes the values measured in the SUDOE MONTCLIMA project in 2020, 2021 and 2022. The data from 2024 shows an unusual pattern that is difficult to explain, as the crown hazard changes slowly and the differences between years should be less evident. The only explanation is that the field team in 2024 overestimated the crown fire hazard compared to previous years. The values in 2025 seem more consistent with the expected results. The results show a moderate crown fire hazard in all treatments and no clear effect of management in reducing the hazard. Longer monitoring is needed to draw conclusions about changes in crown fire hazard.

Table 50. Forest fuel continuity (FFC) model and crown fire (CF) hazard in 2024 and 2025.

Practices	Treatment	2020		2022		2024		2025	
		FFC model	CF hazard	FFC model	CF hazard	FFC model	CF hazard	FFC model	CF hazard
Conventional practices	Irregular forest management	B3-B9-B10	Moderate	B14-B15	Moderate	A4-B14-B15	High-Moderate	B11-B15-C17	Moderate-Low
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature					A3-C15	High-Low	B15-C13	Moderate-Low
	Natural dynamics					A3-B9	Moderate-High	B10-B11-B14	Moderate
Control		A3-B3-B9	Moderate-High	B9	Moderate	A3-B10	Moderate-High	B10-B15-B16	Moderate

Figure 9. Graphic representation of the forest fuel continuity models present in Montnegre (Source: (Piqué, et al., 2011).

Table 51 shows the understorey biovolume in Montnegre. The initial situation is very similar for all the treatments, except the natural dynamics' treatment, with values ranging from 550.8 to 2097.7 m³/ha.

Table 51. Understorey biovolume in each practice and treatment plots.

Practices	Treatment	Biovolume 2024 (m ³ /ha)
Conventional practices	Irregular forest management	2097.7
New CSF practices	Close-to-Nature	1319.0
	Natural dynamics	550.8
Control		2051.1

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